

DAMAGE VISUAL INDICATION SYSTEM FOR POLYMER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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General idea

The general aim of the study was to improve exploitation safety and simplify structural testing process of polymer composites in constructions.

The specific aim of the study was to develop a damage visual indication system (DVIS) for polymer composite and validate it.

Materials and Technology used for the DVIS

- Mixture in ratio 2:1:
 - microcapsules with leuco dyes;
 - microcapsules with colour developer;
- Impregnation of nylon fabric in the mixture, using rubber roller.
- Dried for at least 6 h at room temperature.

Experiments

- Testing of microcapsules:
 - SEM analysis.
 - TGA measurement.
 - AFM testing.
- Testing of the DVIS as an external layer:
 - The optimal amount of microcapsules was defined.
 - The colour with the best visual response was selected.
- Testing of the DVIS as an internal layer:
 - The effect of integrated DVIS on mechanical properties of composite.

Results

Microcapsules

- Average diameter is $D1 \approx 7 \mu\text{m}$ for m/c with dye and $D2 \approx 2 \mu\text{m}$ for m/c with developer.
- Shell thickness of m/c is $h \approx 0.10 \mu\text{m}$.
- Microcapsules showed thermal stability till $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.
- Ability to change colour kept till $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Damage visual indication system

- Sensitive layers were tested to estimate colour change (visual response) vs. time after load at different temperatures ($-20, +11, +21, +38 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).
- Typical visual response curve vs. time after applied load are presented.

The nominal concentration of the m/c in the dispersion is 40%.
- Specimens with m/c concentrations from 2.7% till 40% were manufactured.
- Sensitive layers were tested by compression tests with 400 N load.

- Sensitive layers with different colour microcapsules (red, green, blue, and black colour microcapsules) were manufactured.
- Sensitive layers were tested by compression tests.

